

A simple process-based model to predict methane emission from flooded fields

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Making reliable predictions of CH₄ fluxes in a changing environment calls for understanding of the processes and interactions involved. This understanding can best be expressed as a mathematical model. We set up a simple model of CH₄ production, consumption, and transport in flooded soil and tested it against data measured in the field (Fig. 1). We hoped to be able to simulate diurnal flux variations over periods of a few days: success would indicate that the essential features of the system have been captured in the model, which could then be refined.

Our model considers only two species (oxygen and CH₄) and makes the following assumptions: the area of the system is homogeneous; transport occurs only by diffusion; all microbial reactions obey dual-substrate Michaelis-Menten kinetics; methanogenesis is inhibited by oxygen; and temperature affects reaction potentials, solubilities, and diffusion

1. Measured and modeled methane fluxes over time.

constants. Potential rates of oxygen consumption, CH₄ production, and CH₄ oxidation were measured in the laboratory by incubating segmented core samples. Michaelis constants and inhibition thresholds were taken from the literature.

Temperatures measured at different depths over 4 d were used to drive the

2. Modeled methane concentrations at different soil depths.

model. Apparent activation energies were adjusted to optimize the fit between measured and modeled fluxes. (See Figure 2 for the simulated CH₄ concentration profiles.) The model appears to behave reasonably well, although peak fluxes are not reproduced. It should form a useful basis for future elaboration. ■

Possibilities for reducing methane emission from ricefields in China

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This discussion on possible ways to reduce CH₄ emission from irrigated rice in China is based on data from Sino-American scientific and technological cooperation (1990-92) and studies by Wang (1993).

International irrigation. Irrigated ricefields make up 92% of the total in China. Using intermittent irrigation saves 30% of the water required for conventional flood-irrigation and increases production by about 10-20%, CH₄ emission could be reduced in different soil conditions by 15.59% with intermittent irrigation (Table 1). Even when

organic fertilizer was three times that of the control field in Nanjing, for example, intermittent irrigation still lowered CH₄ emission by 12%.

Ridge culture. China began introducing ridge culture for rice production in 1983 because the area under water is decreased. Ridging could reduce CH₄ emission by 39-43% (Table 1). Even when organic fertilizer was doubled, the rate was still reduced by 31%.

Although furrowing requires relatively more labor, ridge culture can generally increase production by 20-30% and raise farmers' income by 15%. The area under ridge culture has been expanding rapidly in recent years.

Dry seeded rice. Since the 1970s, dry seeded rice has been introduced to some ricefields in northern China to save 30-60% of the water normally used. Tests showed that dry seeding could reduce CH₄ emission by 59-74% (Table 1).

Although yield was 10% lower than that of transplanted rice, dry seeding showed great potential for reducing CH₄ emission.

Selecting CH₄ emission-reducing varieties. An experiment at Nanjing compared CH₄ emission from hybrid and conventional rices in 1991 (Table 2). The hybrid reduced CH₄ emission by 28% and raised yield by 45% compared with conventional rice. Wang (1993) found that hybrid rice reduced CH₄ emission by 13.4%.

Rational fertilizer application.
a) Organic fertilizer: The quantity and type of organic manure is the dominant factor affecting CH₄ emission. Wang (1993) found that using fermented and "old" sludge from biogas pits could reduce CH₄ emission by 26.7%. More than 5 million rural households are using biogas pits: this technology is being popularized in other areas.